

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MUHAMMAD FUZULI IN SALMAN MUMTAZ'S RESEARCH

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Abstract

The article is dedicated to the work of Salman Mumtaz, one of the founders of Azerbaijani literary studies and folklore studies, who devoted his entire creative life to the study of national literature, an inseparable branch of world literary art. Salman Mumtaz conducted research on world-renowned figures such as Nizami Ganjavi, Imadeddin Nasimi, Mirza Shafi Vazeh, and many other writers and poets. One of the literary artists that Salman Mumtaz researched and valued as a national and spiritual wealth of our nation is the great Azerbaijani poet Muhammad Fuzuli (1494-1556). In 1925, he dedicated the article "Conqueror of Hearts" to the aforementioned poet, published in the 111th issue of the "Communist" newspaper dated May 18. Salman Mumtaz notes that M.Fuzuli came into being and acquired his talent through the mercy of nature. It is through nature's mercy that the qualities expressed by terms such as intelligence, genius, talent, and gift, which are used in the language of many nations. Nature bestows this quality only upon those it favors, those whom it loves and shows kindness to. Omirus in the ancient Greek country, Ferdowsi, the author of the famous "Shahname" in Iran, Moliere in France, Shakespeare in England, Navai in Turkestan, Muhammad Fuzuli in Azerbaijan are considered to be the favorite children of nature. When nature selects them, it does not consider wealth, power, status, or noble lineage; it does not differentiate between the rural or urban, nor does it discriminate based on race or nationality. At one moment, it transforms a simple villager from the town of Tus with sandals on his feet into Abul-Qasim Ferdowsi, reviving a dead nation through his genius, at another, it brings the butcher's son, Shakespeare, into existence, reigniting the dimming flame of English literature with his brilliance, it then elevates Moliere, the son of a quilt-maker, to bring joy to Western stages, leading the French to prosperity, it makes the ordinary accountant Alisher Navoi the leader of Chagatai and Tatar literature, and finally, it takes the relatively unknown Molla Muhammad Baghir from Azerbaijan and, bestowing upon him the exalted title of Sultan of Poets, Fuzuli, spreads the essence of Azerbaijani identity across the world.

Keywords: Salman Mumtaz's research, Fuzuli's artistry, the grace of nature, spiritual wealth.

The world-renowned Fuzuli, through his creative works, has captured the attention of many scientists worldwide, including Hammer, Hartman, Gibb, Huart, Lazarev, and Turkish scientists such as Ali Nihat Tarlan, Hasibe Mazioghlu, Abdulkadir Karahan, and Necmeddin Halil Onan. Salman Mumtaz is also among the researchers who studied this great artist, and the conclusions he presented serve as a significant source for subsequent studies.

Introduction - Salman Mumtaz and Muhammad Fuzuli. Salman Mumtaz (1874-1941), one of the founders of 20th-century Azerbaijani literary research and folklore studies, was born in the ancient city of Shaki, Azerbaijan, after losing his father at the age of three, he moved with his family to Ashgabat, Turkmenistan, returning to his homeland only in 1918. His interest in literature, combined with his proficiency in Russian, Arabic, Persian, and Urdu, gave him the ability to study the masterpieces of world literature's greatest artists. After returning to his homeland, he followed the history of the development of national literature and gathered comprehensive information about many literary figures, perhaps for the first time, presenting this knowledge to the academic community. He achieved significant success in the field of research until he became a victim of the repression of the Soviet empire in 1937. He conducted new scientific research

on the main representatives of classical literature, Nizami Ganjavi, Imadeddin Nasimi, Muhammad Fuzuli, Shah Ismayil Khatai, Mollah Panah Vagif and dozens of famous artists, and made them available to the scientific community. Salman Mumtaz conducted extensive research on various genres of folk literature and published his conclusions in this field in the form of articles. Regrettably, a large part of these invaluable samples of the people's speech treasure was destroyed due to his repression after 1937 and his death in prison in 1941 [4, 57-61]. One of the literary artists that Salman Mumtaz researched and valued as a national and spiritual wealth of our nation is the great Azerbaijani poet Muhammad Fuzuli. "Fuzuli is the most prominent representative of poetry in the Azerbaijani language during the medieval period of Azerbaijani literature. The poet carefully studied the rich culture created in various languages by the peoples of the Near and Middle East before him and observed his environment under the light of that culture, creating a rich and multifaceted legacy. Fuzuli, who created works with unattainable artistic features in various forms of Eastern poetry in Azerbaijani, Persian and Arabic languages, is distinguished above all by his deep humanism" Although he spent his entire life in the town of Karbala in Baghdad, he composed his famous works in his native Azerbaijani language, including the poem

"Leyli and Majnun," and contributed to the enrichment of Azerbaijan's spiritual heritage. For this reason, Salman Mumtaz dedicated the article "Conqueror of Hearts" to Muhammad Fuzuli, published in the 111th issue of the "Communist" newspaper on May 18, 1925.

Salman Mumtaz: "Geniuses are born from the grace of nature". The article begins with a verse from the poet Doctor Sanan, which introduces the theme of the article. It is emphasized in the poem that if the Sun needs years to acquire a single bright precious stone - pearl, durri-badakhshan, red Yemeni ring-brow, it takes centuries to make a gifted child a perfect speaker. In other words, geniuses are not born all the time, it takes centuries for their creation. Salman Mumtaz extends the idea from the poem, emphasizing that geniuses are not born all the time and that their emergence requires centuries. He notes in the article that "nature does not bestow such grace upon everyone at all times, nor does it look upon every person with such favor. Thousands of teachers and students from madrassas and higher education institutions have obtained certificates and diplomas after completing their education. However, only a small part of the city or town where they reside recognizes them. To achieve worldwide fame, the grace and mercy of nature are necessary" [7, 5]. It is precisely through the mercy of nature that qualities such as intelligence, genius, inspiration, talent, gift, and aptitude - terms used in many languages - are formed in many nations. Nature bestows this quality only upon those it favors and deems worthy, without any discrimination based on religion, race, nationality, etc. If we look closely, we see that many enlightened individuals from various cultures around the world have emerged, and the knowledge and spiritual treasures they have contributed have served not only their own people but also the advancement of humanity as a whole. Omirus in the ancient Greek country, Ferdowsi, the author of the famous "Shahname" in Iran, Moliere in France, Shakespeare in England, Navai in Turkestan, Muhammad Fuzuli in Azerbaijan are considered to be the favorite children of nature. As long as the world endures, humanity will remember these renowned figures, appreciating their multifaceted contributions and recognizing their role in shaping future generations correctly. Salman Mumtaz, as is evident, holds these world-famous talents in great esteem and notes that such figures gifted to humanity will not emerge again. When nature selects them, "it does not consider wealth, power, status, or noble lineage; it does not distinguish between rural and urban, nor does it discriminate based on race or nationality. At one moment, it transforms a simple villager from the town of Tus with worn sandals into Abul-Qasim Ferdowsi, reviving a dead nation through his genius, at another, it brings the butcher's son, Shakespeare, into existence, reigniting the fading flame of English literature with his brilliance, it then raises Moliere, the son of a quilt-maker, to bring joy to Western stages, leading the French to prosperity, it makes the ordinary accountant Alisher Navoi the leader of Chagatai and Tatar literature, finally, it takes the relatively unknown Molla Muhammad Baghir from Azerbaijan and, bestowing upon him the exalted title of Sultan of Poets,

Fuzuli, spreads the essence of Azerbaijani identity across the world..." [5, 338]. Salman Mumtaz, with a sense of pride, notes that Fuzuli's genius gaining worldwide fame has led other Azerbaijanis to stand in the same esteemed position. This event helps fill everyone with a sense of pride. It becomes clear from this that great artists who achieve global recognition are those who support the renaissance of their own national literature. The renaissance is an indicator of the formation of literature in a national spirit. Particularly, the tradition of writing and creating in one's native language is one of the main driving forces of the renaissance. His work has attracted the attention of many scientists worldwide, including Hammer, Hartman, Gibb, Huart, Lazarev, and Turkish scientists such as Ali Nihat Tarlan, Hasibe Mazioghlu, Abdulkadir Karahan, and Necmeddin Halil Onan. This is not only due to Fuzuli's unique art of language but also because of his ability to write and create in three languages - Arabic, Persian, and Azerbaijani - with the same intonation. However, since works written in Arabic and Persian gained more fame in the Middle Ages, there were few who wrote in their native language. The poet, striving to demonstrate the power of the native language, would write works in his mother tongue whenever possible and attempt to express its glory. Thus, in one of his works, Muhammad Fuzuli states that

O Feyz Rasan Arab Turku-Ajam,
Qildin Arabi-Afsah Ahli-Alam.
You did fusahayi-ajam, Isa,
Don't compliment in turki-zaban [5, 338].

The article highlights this literary example to express Muhammad Fuzuli's love for his native language. The eminent researcher said: "He cared for his native tongue like a parent thinking of their child's future, bringing light to their day and making the difficult easy," and provides another example of the work of the poet in the article:

Thus, in Persian verse, there's much composed with ease,

The poem is gentle, with a Turkish accent.

He composed the dialect-Turkish, the reception-verse,

Most of the time, alpha-namarbuti is uneven.

If I find success, I'll make this hardship light,
As in spring, from thorns, flowers bloom in sight [5, 339].

One of the noteworthy points here is the information provided about the ethnicity of Muhammad Fuzuli. Salman Mumtaz states, "Although it is beyond the scope of our discussion, let us clarify which group of Turks the great Fuzuli belonged to. Since this is a disputed matter, I must present evidence from Fuzuli's own works: "The expectation is that, in general, the people of honor and respect, particularly the eloquent of Rum and the rhetoricians of the Tatars, will excuse this claim if the words in my expressions

are not adorned with the elegance of those lands, and if the verses in my poetry are not embellished with the subtleties and proverbs of those realms" [5, 339]. In one of his articles, Pasha Adiloghlu notes that "The great Fuzuli, who highlighted the differences between Turkish languages, referred to his own language as Turkish in the preface of his divan written in his mother tongue. He called Ottoman poets 'bulaghayi-Rum' and Central Asian artists 'fusahayi-Tatar.' Similarly, Sadiq bey Afshar referred to the Ottomans as 'bulaghayi-Rum' and the Central Asian Turks as 'fusahayi-Chagatai.'" [2]. From this, it can be concluded that M. Fuzuli was not a representative of the "bulagayi-Rum" or "fusahayi-Tatar" regions. Muhammad Fuzuli was an Azerbaijani Turk. Mehmet Fuat Koprulu, one of the Turkish scientists of Fuzuli, introduced him as an Azerbaijani poet in the preface he wrote for Fuzuli's divan in 1924 [8, 284]. Mehmet Omer Gazanchi writes, "The reason for Fuzuli's works being read with such interest is not only his ability to write in Arabic, Persian, and Turkish, but also the fact that the themes he addressed were different for that time, and the author approached events from a unique perspective." His language, being closer to the conversational style of Turkish and adhering correctly to the fundamental structures of the Turkish language, as well as his unique approach compared to poets of his time, further enhances the readability of his works. Although the influence of Azerbaijani and Kerkuk Turkish is clearly evident in the Turkish he used, the traces of Chagatai and Ottoman Turkish are also apparent" [3, 6].

Muhammad Fuzuli and folklore. Muhammad Fuzuli is a universal poet whose works enrich the global treasury of literature. He is also a beloved poet of the Turkish world. However, as Salman Mumtaz puts it, M. Fuzuli is a prominent representative of Azerbaijani literature, and this view is confirmed by the mentioned scientists in one way or another. Salman Mumtaz also firmly confirms this conclusion. In our opinion, this is the correct approach. This is because legends and discussions have been told from time to time about artists who emerged in Azerbaijan and were closely followed with interest in nearby and distant regions, as well as in the literary communities of the Near and Middle East and the global scientific circulation. Often, such artists not only drew inspiration from folklore throughout their creative careers but were also valued as significant sources for folklore themselves. The tales circulating about Nizami Ganjavi, Nesimi, Shah Ismail Khatai, and M.P. Vagif are prominent examples of this. Similarly, the folklore surrounding Muhammad Fuzuli characterizes him as a folkloric Azerbaijani and literary figure. One of the legends about him is called "Hind arx". The content of the legend is that Muhammad Fuzuli's family lived near the village of Hindarx in the Aghcabadi district, one of the ancient regions of Azerbaijan. This could have been one of the oldest settlements in our country, currently known as Boyat village in the Aghcabadi district. The issue of Fuzuli being from the Boyat region is consistently a topic of interest in sources. Salman Mumtaz himself unambiguously accepts that Fuzuli hailed from the

Boyat region [6, 7-20]. An architect from India, Fuzuli's father Suleyman, comes to the area where the man lives, stays there for a while, and marries Fuzuli's sister. During this time, to help the locals who are struggling to irrigate their fields, the Indian craftsman constructs a canal from the Gargar river to the fields. Following this, people settle in these newly fertile lands, and the village begins to be called Hindarx in honor of the Hindu engineer. Subsequently, due to disputes and disturbances with the neighbors, Suleyman and his family move to Karbala with the guidance of his son-in-law, the Hindu engineer.

This story circulating in the language of ordinary people once again confirms that Muhammad Fuzuli is an Azerbaijani.

Salman Mumtaz's research on Muhammad Fuzuli, one of the powerful figures in Azerbaijani literature, is of particular importance. The world-renowned artist is not only celebrated for his position in written literature but has also made exceptional contributions to the enrichment of Azerbaijani folklore. Today, expressions like "I offered a greeting, but they didn't accept it, saying it wasn't a bribe," "Fuzuli climbed the mountain out of sorrow, and they said: 'He must have gone to the highlands of fortune,'" and "Do not flow like water to everyone you see" are related to Fuzuli's art and personality. In Fuzuli's poems "Leyli and Majnun," "Dahname," as well as in his allegorical works such as "Bengu Bade," "Sahhat and Meraz," "Sohbetul-asmara," and "Seven glass," elements of folk epic traditions, legends, and narratives are reflected. In the work "Bengu Bade," the reference to the widely circulated "Sheikh Sanan" legend from Near Eastern folklore when discussing wine, the motifs of Noah's Ark, the Water of Life of the Prophet Khidr, and Jamshid's cup in "Seven glass," as well as Fuzuli's own expression at the beginning of "Sahhat and Meraz," where he says, "one of those who laid the foundation of the tale says and narrates...", and the use of narrative style, are examples of this [9].

Salman Mumtaz's research on representatives of Azerbaijani literature at the beginning of the 20th century was aimed not only at introducing well-known literary figures to the readership but also at ensuring that the entire Azerbaijani people would recognize and cherish their national heritage and spiritual wealth, which is the treasure of their literary legacy. Araz Dadashzade's thoughts on this matter are of great interest: "The great Fuzuli's poetry, of course, could not escape S. Mumtaz's attention. In his articles dedicated to the poet, Mumtaz discussed Fuzuli's Azerbaijani origin and the place of his poetry in the literature of Turkic-speaking peoples. One of Mumtaz's significant contributions in this field was the first scientific-critical edition of Fuzuli's Azerbaijani divan, based on the manuscript kept in Baku. This edition was compared by the prominent Soviet orientalist Y. Bertels with the manuscript copy in Leningrad." [1, 115].

Conclusion. Salman Mumtaz has rendered important services in the development of Azerbaijani literary studies.

At the beginning of the 20th century, there was a need for a systematic reexamination of the Azerbaijani

poet Muhammad Fuzuli, and in this context, Salman Mumtaz's articles and conclusions hold particular significance.

Salman Mumtaz's research on Fuzuli has been a significant source for further research.

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